

Upper Gastro Intestinal Bleed – Causes, Endoscopic Profile and Usefulness of Rockall Score in Determining the Outcome (Mortality and Rebleeding)Srivastava S¹, Katira HB², Rathod JB³, Jayeshkumar B. Bagada⁴^{1,2,3}Department of General Surgery, PSMC and Shree Krishna hospital, karamsad-388325, Dist-Anand, Gujarat⁴Department of General Surgery, GMERS Medical College and Civil Hospital, Himmatnagar-383001

Received: 18-08-2024 / Revised: 21-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

Corresponding author: Dr. Jayeshkumar B. Bagada

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Upper Gastrointestinal (UGI) haemorrhage is one of the common emergencies met in clinical practice. The mode of presentation is diverse and depends on the cause and the amount of blood loss. Early upper gastrointestinal endoscopy, defined as within 24 hours of hospital presentation or admission is the cornerstone of management of UGIB. Early endoscopy helps in diagnosis, treatment and risk stratification. Therapeutic endoscopy is considered a safe and effective form of treatment today.

Objective: To study endoscopic findings and determining the outcomes (mortality and rebleeding) in patients presenting with Upper Gastrointestinal Bleed (UGIB) and in patients on blood thinners in our institute.

Methods and Material: A total of 56 patients who were referred to emergency department of Shree Krishna Hospital Gokalnagar in the district of Anand of state of Gujarat which is a part of western India were properly managed and were subjected to therapeutic and diagnostic endoscopy were included in this prospective cross-sectional study and were studied for 6 months.

Results: In the studied population among 56 patients, the most common cause of UGIB was variceal bleed 45 (80%); than that of non-variceal bleed 11(20%). The mean Rockall score was 4.7 which indicated that most patients belong to moderate risk group.

Conclusion: Rockall score helped in identifying that most of the patients belonged to moderate and high risk group. The mortality was significantly high in the high risk group compared to the low and moderate risk group in which there were no mortality.

Keywords: Upper Gastrointestinal Bleed (UGIB), Varices, Hematemesis, Melena.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding is an extremely common clinical problem resulting in more than 3,00,000 hospitalizations annually in the United States. The overall incidence of upper GI bleeding is approximately 125 hospitalizations for every 1,00,000 people, with a male to female ratio of 2:1[1]. Bleeding from upper GI tract is five times as common as lower GI bleed.

Mortality from acute GI bleeding is much greater than that for chronic bleeding. Therefore, it is important to understand the pathogenesis of acute GI bleeding, with an emphasis on early detection, prevention and intervention, in order to minimize morbidity and mortality. The clinical presentation reflects the site, aetiology and rate of bleeding and may manifest in one or more ways. Hematemesis, melena and haematochezia are the most common manifestations. The bleeding may be obscure in about 5% of cases and at times may manifest as an

occult bleed. Peptic ulcers are the most common causes of upper GI bleeding and are followed by variceal bleeding, gastric and duodenal erosive disease and Mallory-Weiss tears in prevalence. The associated factors include H. pylori infection, NSAID intake and alcohol abuse.

Many guidelines recommend long-term use of aspirin for prevention of cardiovascular events among patients with prior cardiovascular disease or multiple risk factors. However, aspirin is associated with increased risk of major gastrointestinal bleeding. A recent meta-analysis found an approximately two-fold higher risk of gastrointestinal bleeding among individuals regularly using aspirin compared to placebo. An initial hemodynamic assessment helps to plan resuscitation, forms the basis of further management and also predicts the prognosis of the patient. Analysis of clinical and endoscopic factors

permits accurate risk assessment, rational treatment planning and improved outcome.

A number of scoring systems have been designed to ascertain risk factors for poor outcome and to improve patient management and promote cost-effective use of hospital resources in patients with UGIB. Rockall et al [2,3] developed a risk-scoring system involving clinical and endoscopic criteria to predict the risk of rebleeding and mortality in patients with UGIB.

It is based on age, presence of shock, co-morbidity, diagnosis and endoscopic stigmata of recent haemorrhage. Multiple studies have validated the Rockall score's ability to identify and risk-stratify patients with UGIB. The Rockall system has been shown to represent an accurate and valid predictor of rebleeding and death. This has the potential to result in a more appropriate management of subjects' conditions based on their assessed risk of complications following the initial UGI bleed.

Materials and Methodology

Fifty six patients with Upper GI bleed came to Shree Krishna Hospital were patients were first evaluated and investigated. Clinical examination was done. The patients who were in shock, were first stabilized with appropriate management like iv fluids and blood products transfusion and routine blood investigation like CBC, Electrolyte, ABG, LFT etc. Imaging studies like USG A+P, Chest X ray and CT scan were done as per the requirement of the patient. Patient were admitted in the ICU with RT insertion and gastric lavage and aspiration was done. Once the patient were stable, Upper GI Scopy was done for diagnostic and therapeutic intent. This helped us in determining the Rock All score of the patient and helped us in assessing the outcome based on the score. The design of the study was prospective cross-sectional study. The period of study was of 6 months and ethical clearance was obtained and informed consent was taken of all patients.

Patient Selection

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients with upper GI bleed (hematemesis, melena, hemato-chezia)
2. The patients who fulfilled the above mentioned criteria and did not have any contraindications for endoscopy and were willing for undergoing upper GI endoscopy will be enrolled in study.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Comatose Patients
2. Patients With Stage 3 And 4 Hepatic Encephalopathy
3. Perforated Viscus
4. Those who didn't gave consent for UGI scopy.

Protocol

1. All patients who met the above criteria were included in the study the following were noted in each patient
2. Age
3. Gender
4. Presentation- hematemesis, melena, haematochezia
5. Severity of bleed-minor, moderate or massive
 - Minor bleed-no hemodynamic instability, <10% blood loss
 - Moderate bleed - postural hypotension and orthostatic tachycardia, 10-20% intravascular volume loss
 - Massive bleed-shock (resting hypotension) - 20-25% intravascular volume loss
 - Associated factors-Alcohol use, smoking, use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID), corrosive ingestion and past history of upper GI bleed
6. Comorbid conditions –Ischemic heart disease, congestive cardiac failure, renal failure, liver disease, disseminated malignancy
7. Physical examination and documentation of tachycardia and hypotension and the clinical diagnosis
8. Requirement for blood transfusion

Endoscopy

Upper GI endoscopy was performed in all patients, findings documented and requirement and mode of endoscopic therapy to control bleeding in indicated cases, noted.

Varices were classified by the classification proposed by Sarin et al. The grading of oesophageal varices was taken as follows: small and straight (grade I); tortuous and occupying less than one third of the oesophageal lumen (grade II); or large and occupying more than one third of the oesophageal lumen (grade III).

Rockall score was calculated in all patients based on the following criteria

- Age
- Shock (assessed from pulse rate and blood pressure)
- Comorbid conditions (cardiac, renal, liver, others)
- Endoscopic stigmata of recent bleed
- Endoscopic diagnosis

On summing up different levels of a point grading system, scores ranging from 0 to 11 were obtained. Rebleed was defined as fresh hematemesis or melena associated with the development of shock or a fall in haemoglobin concentration of at least 2 g/dl in 2 hours. The rebleed, requirement of blood transfusions and mortality were documented and

the efficacy of Rockall score as a predictor of rebleed was analysed. The concordance between the initial clinical diagnosis and endoscopic findings were recorded.

Statistical analysis -Fisher's exact test as appropriate were used for comparison between groups. A P value of 0.05 or less was regarded as significant.

Results

Table 1: Mode of Presentation

Age	Presentation					No. of cases
	Haematemesis	Melena	Haematemesis+Melena	Haematemesis+Melena+Haematochezia	Haematemesis+Haematochezia	
20-39	7		3			10(17.8%)
40-59	14	3	4		3	24 (42.8%)
60-79	12	3	5	1		21(37.5%)
>80	1					1(1.7%)
Total	34(60.7%)	6(10.7%)	12(21.4%)	1(1.7%)	3(5.3%)	56

Table 2: Severity of Bleed

Age	Severity			No. of cases
	Minor	Moderate	Severe	
20-39	4	4	2	10(17.8%)
40-59	12	8	4	24 (42.8%)
60-79	9	9	3	21(37.5%)
>80			1	1(1.7%)
Total	25(44.6%)	21(37.5%)	10 (17.8%)	56

In the study population of 56 patients, around 44 patients (75%) had comorbidity out of which; 18 of them (32.1% of population) had liver disease which contributed to the UGIB. Other comorbidities included Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease,

Diabetes mellitus and systemic hypertension; which contributed 11 (19.6%) of population. Around 4 patients (7.1%) had cardiac problems like ischemic heart disease and congestive cardiac failure.

Table 3: Timing of Endoscopy

	Early (within 24 hours)	Late (after 24 hours)	Grand Total
Timing of Endoscopy	43(76.7%)	13(27.8%)	56

Endoscopic Findings: Variceal causes predominated and was the most common sources of bleed in all age categories.

Table 4: Cause of Bleed

	Causes		Grand Total
	Varices	Non-Variceal	
Count of V/NV	45(80.3%)	11(19.6%)	56

Table 5: Non Variceal Causes

No. of Endoscopic Findings	Non-variceal cause								Grand Total
	Dieulofoy's lesion	Duodenal Ulcer	Gastritis	Oesophageal Ulcer	MW Tear	Gastric Ulcer	Normal	Duodenitis+Gastric ulcer	
	1(1.7%)	1(1.7%)	2(3.5%)	2(3.5%)	1(1.7%)	1(1.7%)	2(3.5%)	1(1.7%)	11

Grade of varices: Grade 3 shows 23 cases which accounts for (52.2%) of whole study. Grade 2 varices are present in 14 patients (31.8%) and grade 1 varices are present in 7 patients (15.9%).

Table 6: Rockall score and outcome

Variable	Risk group			No of cases
	Low Risk (A)	Moderate Risk (B)	High Risk (C)	
PRBC (packed red blood cells)	1	18	22	41
Rebleed	1	5	20	26
Mortality	0	0	2	2

The need for packed red cell transfusion and the number of patients who had rebleed were noted, along with mortality. Mortality was seen only in high risk group.

Table 7: Risk groups and outcome – comparison

	low vs moderate risk (p value)	low vs high risk (p value)
PRBC (packed red blood cells)	<0.05	<0.05
Rebleed	>0.05	<0.05
Mortality	<0.05	0.544

This table shows comparison of various modalities in various risk groups. The requirement of blood transfusion was significantly higher in the moderate and high risk groups as compared to the low risk groups, (both P values less than 0.05). The incidence of rebleed which was less in the moderate risk group (P value >0.05) and the incidence of rebleed was more in high risks group. (P value <0.05). There was no mortality in the moderate and low risk groups. There were 2 deaths in the third group statistically significant as compared to the low risk group and moderate risk group. (p value= 0.544). All of the 56 patients underwent endotherapy. Out of which 41 patients were treated with EVL, 3 patients received EST and only 2 patients were treated with injection therapy with adrenaline. It was noted that out of the 56 cases 26 patients had rebleed. The rebleed was found to be only in variceal causes. No rebleed was found in non-variceal causes. All of the 26 patients who had rebleed, received endotherapy for the same. All the patients were treated with either EVL or EST or Adrenaline injected locally to control bleeding.

Discussion

The clinical and endoscopic profile of the four hundred and six patients presenting to the endoscopy unit of the institution were analysed. Age, gender, severity of bleed, mode of presentation, etiology and associated factors were documented, along with the documentation of Rockall score, requirement of blood transfusions, rebleed and endotherapy instituted. The Rockall score has been validated by several studies, for predicting rebleed and mortality.

In this study, along with the determination of the Rockall score, the subjects were divided into three risk groups. The available data is compared with contemporary literature and utility of Rockall score in risk stratification, is evaluated.

The mean age was 53.1 years with an age range of 20-82 years. It was lower than that observed in the RUGBE (Canadian Registry on Upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding and Endoscopy Database of 1869 patients) study by Barkun et al [4], Rockall and Logan [2,3] et al. and Yavorski et al[5].

Table 8: Age distribution- comparison

	Barkun et al [4]	Rockall et al [2,3]	Yavorski et al [5]	Present study
Mean age	66	66	52.06	53.1
Age range	7-105	16-103	01-999	20-82
Total number	1869	2332	3294	56

The majority of patients in the present study fell into the age group of 40-59 years -24 (42.8%). Only 1 subject (1.7%) was above 80 years, as compared to 634 (27.2%) noted by Rockall et al, who concluded that the incidence of bleed significantly increased with age. Longstreth [6] and colleagues, in their series, noted that 47% of their patients were above 60 years of age, as compared to the present study where it was noted to be only 39.2%. Male predilection (64.2%) was noted in this study, in concordance with the RUGBE database, where 62% were males and that noted by Rockall et al [2,3] (57% males). Longstreth et al [6] also had noted a male predilection of 67.9%.

Majority of patients patients-34(60.7%) had hematemesis as a presenting feature and 6(10.7%) had melena, as compared to RUGBE data where hematemesis was noted in 58% of patients and melena in 69%, and that observed by Longstreth et al [6] who noted that 33% of their patients had

hematemesis and 81% had melena. Hematochezia was noted in 12(21.4%), which was higher than that noted by Barkun et al (15%1) [4]. Longstreth et al [6] noted history of NSAID (aspirin) use in 53% and alcohol use in 3% of patients in their series. The present study noted a much higher percentage of patients with alcohol use- 28(50%), though NSAID (aspirin) use was noted only in 5(8.9%) of patients. Chak et al [7] observed that early endoscopy was done in 82% of their patients. Rockall et al [2,3] noted that 1108(50.1%) patients underwent early endoscopy which was comparable to that noted in the present study 43(76.7%). Barkun et al [4] noted in the RUGBE study, that 56% had peptic ulcer disease as the primary etiology for UGI bleeding, followed by esophagitis (8.4%), Mallory Weiss tears (4.4%) and Dieulafoy lesions (2.5%). In the present study, 11 patients had non-variceal causes of bleed, of which peptic ulcers

accounted for 1(1.7%). 1(1.7%) had duodenal ulcers and 2(3.5%) had gastric ulcers.

Gastritis-2(3.5%) and duodenitis 1(1.7%) were seen, with oesophageal ulcer seen in 2(3.5%), much were much less than that noted by Barkun et al [4] Mallory Weiss tears accounted for 1(1.7%) cases. In the present study variceal cause predominated in causing UGIB than non-variceal causes in all the age groups, but it was found more significantly higher in patients less than 60 years of age than >60 years of age. Varices were observed in a much lower percentage by Rockall et al [2,3] and

Vreeburg [8] (4.6% and 9% respectively), in comparison with this study (80.3%). Endotherapy was done in all 56 (100%) cases in the present study. Adrenaline injection was performed in just 2 cases, Endoscopic sclerotherapy was done in just 3 cases and in majority of patients endoscopic variceal ligation (41) was done. Vreeburg et al [8] in their series, noted lower endoscopic intervention rates, with 21% of patients with UGIB in their case series undergoing endotherapy. The mean Rockall score was 4.8 in the RUGBE study whereas in the present study, it was mean score: 4.7 indicating that most patients belonged to the moderate risk category.

Table 9: Risk groups based on Rockall Score

RISK	RUGBE [4]	Rockall et al [2,3]	Present study
Low	240(13%)	1058(45.4%)	8(14.2%)
Moderate	999(53%)	1181(50.7%)	25(44.6%)
High	630(34%)	93(3.9%)	23(41.07%)
Total	1869	2332	56

As compared to the RUGBE study [4] where the majority belonged to the moderate and high risk group, in the present study, here in present study also most of the patients had a high Rockall score (more than 3) and belonged to the moderate risk group. However, the percentage of patients belonging to the high risk group, in the present study, was higher than that noted by Rockall et al [2,3] (41.07% vs. 3.9%) as patients in high risk group had more of esophageal varices than gastric varices.

Table 10: Comorbidity and hemodynamic instability

	Rockall et al [2,3]	Present study
Comorbidity	1378(59.1%)	34(60.17%)
Hypotension	256(11.2%)	14(25%)

The comorbidities were higher in the present study (60.17%) as compared to that noted by Rockall et al [2,3] (59.1%), and Yavorski et al [5] (50.9%) and hemodynamic instability was also higher (25%) than that noted by Rockall et al (11.2%) as patients were mostly alcoholic and had chronic liver parenchymal disease.

In the present study, the requirement of blood transfusion was significantly higher in the moderate and high risk groups as compared to the low risk groups, (both P values less than 0.05), as was the

incidence of rebleed which was more in the moderate and high risk groups as against the low risk group. Akash et al [09], in their study of upper GI bleed, from a tertiary care institution at Chennai, also noted that Rockall score correlated well with the need for blood transfusions, rebleeding and mortality.

In the present study, the rebleed rate in moderate risk group was 19.2% and slightly lower than that noted by Akash et al [09] (21.4%) but the rate of rebleed in the high risk group was higher.

Table 11: Risk groups and rebleed- comparison

RISK	RUGBE [4]	PRESENT STUDY
Low	21(8.8%)	1(3.8%)
Moderate	130(13%)	5(19.2%)
High	107(17%)	20(76.9%)
Total	258	26

It was noted that in the low risk group, the rebleed was lower in the present study (3.8%) as compared to Rugbe [4] data, where 8.8% rebleed and that noted by Rockall et al [2,3]. 41 where 4.3% had rebleed. But it was observed that in the high risk group, 76.9% of patients had rebleed which was higher than the rate of 17% noted in the RUGBE data. The present study shows that the risk of rebleed in patients on NSAID (aspirin) was nil and there was no mortality associated with it and they

were easily managed by endotherapy. The incidence of mortality was nil in low and moderate risks groups. Only 2 mortality was noted in high risk groups.

Conclusion

Upper GI bleed is an important indication for endoscopic referral to this institute. The majority of the patients were noted to be below 60 years of age with a male predilection. Most of the cases

presented with moderate or severe upper GI bleed with minor bleeds constituting a minority. NSAID and alcohol as well as smoking were the notable associated factors in patients with UGIB. Blood thinners also result in UGIB but the severity of bleed is mild and prognosis of the patients is good and patients are at less risk of rebleed and mortality. Variceal bleed was the most common cause of UGIB presenting with grade II and III varices. It was predominated in middle age group with more male predominant. Non-variceal bleed were distributed in all age group and different cause of non-variceal bleed like oesophageal ulcer, peptic ulcer, duodenal ulcer, Mallory wies tear , duodenitis were identified using endoscopic correlation. Based on Rockall score, most of the case fell into moderate and severe risk groups (score between 3-11). In the moderate group the patients with variceal bleed were higher compared to both high and low risk group. The rebleed was significantly higher in patients with variceal bleed than that of non-variceal bleed. The requirement of packed red blood cell transfusion and rebleed were higher in patients with higher Rockall score (moderate and high risk groups). The mortality was significantly high in the high risk group compared to the low and moderate risk group in which there were no mortality. Hence, Rockall score has been found to correlate well with clinical outcome, including need for transfusions, rebleeding and mortality, and may be used for effective triage of patients into outpatient and inpatient care, as well as to predict prognosis in upper GI bleed.

Bibliography

1. Kim K. Portal hypertensive acute gastrointestinal bleeding. *Acute Gastrointestinal Bleeding- diagnosis and treatment.* Humana Press Inc. 97- 110.
2. Rockall. T A, Logan R F A, Devlin et al. Influencing the practice and outcome in acute upper gastrointestinal haemorrhage. *Gut* 1997; 41;606-611.
3. Rockall TA, Logan RFA, Devlin HB, et al. Risk assessment after acute upper gastrointestinal haemorrhage. *Gut* 1996; 38:316-321.
4. Barkun A, Sabbah S, Enns R et al. The Canadian registry on nonvariceal upper GI bleeding and Endoscopy (RUGBE): endoscopic haemostasis and proton pump inhibition are associated with improved outcomes in a real life setting. *Am. J. Gastro.*2004;99:1238-1246.
5. Yavorski RT, Wong RKH, Analysis of Upper Gastrointestinal bleeding in military medical care facilities. *Am. J Gastro* 1995;vol90:4.
6. Longstreth GF, Feitelberg SP. Outpatient care of selected patients with acute non-variceal upper gastrointestinal haemorrhage. *Lancet* 1995;345(8942):108-11.
7. Chak A, Cooper GS, Lloyd LE et al. Effectiveness of endoscopy in patents admitted to the intensive care unit with Upper GI hemorrhage. *GI endosc.*2001;53:6-13.
8. Vreeburg, E. M., Terwee, C. B., Snel, P., Rauws, E. A. J., Bartelsman, J. F. W. M., Meulen, J. H. P., & Tytgat, G. N. Validation of the Rockall risk scoring system in upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage. *Gut*, 1999; 44, 331-335.
9. Akash C et al. Validation of Rockall score for non-variceal Upper GI bleed study from Chennai. *Indian J Gastroenterol* 2007;26; suppl 2:A13.